

Velocity-Level Kinematics of a Continuously Variable Transmission System for pHRI

Emir Mobedi¹ and Mehmet İsmet Can Dede¹

¹ Izmir Institute of Technology, Mechanical Engineering Department, 35430, İzmir, Türkiye.
{emirmobedi, candede}@iyte.edu.tr

Abstract. New generation robots pave the way for physical human-robot interaction (pHRI) through improvements in control and design techniques. While the former is achieved with the help of a number of sensory information, variable stiffness actuators (VSA) are exploited for the design of these robots to achieve inherent compliance. Recently, continuously variable transmission-based VSA has been developed to be used for pHRI, specifically for haptics. The fundamental characteristic of this new CVT mechanism is that it regulates output position and torque independently via the sphere transmission element. In this study, velocity-level kinematics of this new CVT system is carried out to demonstrate its step-less speed variation feature. Moreover, simulations are conducted in ADAMS and Solidworks software packages at 8 transmission points selected unequally. Results show that the average value of overall ADAMS and Solidworks errors computed with respect to the computed velocity are reported as 1.09 %, and 0.53 %, respectively.

Keywords: Continuously variable transmission (CVT), variable speed mechanism, physical human-robot interface (pHRI).

1 Introduction

Collaborative robots (cobot) have been receiving significant attention over the past two decades thanks to recent advancements on design [1] and control strategies [2]. Unlike the old fashion where robots are confined in a working cell, those improvements allow roboticists to operate robots in the same environment as workers, and even physically interact with them. For instance, progress in control is achieved implementing number of sensory information (e.g. camera and force/torque sensors) together with torque control algorithms. On the other hand, variable transmission mechanisms (i.e., variable stiffness actuators (VSA)) are employed in new robot joint designs [3]. VSA have several design characteristics such as shock absorbing and independent output torque and position change. In such systems, the stiffness is altered by elongating an elastic element (commonly a spring) through a motor whereas the output position is regulated via another motor. Incorporation of a compliant element protects the device and its surroundings from unpredictable impacts and thereby resulting in an intrinsically compliant mechanism.

Recently, a continuously variable transmission (CVT) based VSA has been developed to be employed in pHRI (see Fig.1), specifically in haptics [4]. In conventional CVT systems, there are two variators to transfer power from input to output variator through friction, gear or belt systems [5]. The core advantage CVT mechanisms bring is to carry out stepless torque variation in a predefined working range. Focusing on the CVT with cone-shaped variators, they cannot be employed in pHRI applications due to the transmission element (wheel).

Fig. 1. A) Isometric view of the new CVT system [6].

To clarify, it is not possible to adjust output position independent from output torque because the wheel cannot perform holonomic motion. To overcome this challenge, we changed the wheel with a sphere which is able to carry out holonomic motion [6]. However, another issue emerged for single sphere CVT regarding counterclockwise (CCW) torque transmission. To exemplify, for CW direction, cones enforce the sphere to rotate towards inside the cones and increases the tangential force at the cone-sphere contact point. Yet, for the opposite direction, tangential force pushes the sphere outside of the cones, mitigating the friction force at the contact point. Therefore, another sphere is placed from the bottom part of the cones to achieve bidirectional transmission as in Fig.2B. More detailed explanation can be found in [4].

Even though geometrical [6] and static force analysis [4] of this new CVT mechanism is carried out, its velocity-level kinematics has not been presented yet. In this paper, the velocity of the output cone is derived in terms of the design parameters including R (radius of the sphere), r_1 (minimum cone radius), L (the length of the side of the cone), θ (cone angle), D (the distance between the cone's rotation axes), and the input velocity applied to input cone (ω_{in}). Then, simulations are conducted in ADAMS and Solidworks at 8 different transmission levels selected unequally. Final-

ly, the comparison is presented between the simulative and the theoretical results.

Fig. 2. A) Isometric view of the simulation created in ADAMS 2017.1, B) Double sphere solution illustrated in computer-aided drawings [4].

2 Velocity Level Kinematics

In this section, kinematics of the CVT in velocity-level is carried out step by step considering each element affecting the rotation. Throughout the calculations, all the components are assumed to be completely rigid. To start with, the orientation of the sphere above the cones are sketched considering parameters denoted in Fig.3. Moreover, the inertial reference frame is defined as $\mathcal{F}_2\{\vec{u}_1^{(2)}, \vec{u}_2^{(2)}, \vec{u}_3^{(2)}\}$, and $\hat{C}^{(i,j)}$ is the rotation matrix between the i^{th} and j^{th} frames. The rotation matrices between frames of interest are presented as follows:

$$\hat{C}^{(2,4)} = \hat{C}^{(2,3)}\hat{C}^{(3,4)} = e^{\tilde{u}_2\theta_{11}}e^{\tilde{u}_3\theta_{12}} \quad ; \quad \hat{C}^{(2,6)} = \hat{C}^{(2,5)}\hat{C}^{(5,6)} = e^{\tilde{u}_2\theta_{21}}e^{\tilde{u}_3\theta_{22}} \quad (1)$$

where \tilde{u}_i represents the cross-product matrix (a 3x3 skew-symmetric matrix) of \vec{u}_i , which is the rotation axis vector. θ_j indicates the rotation about \vec{u}_i , and $e^{\tilde{u}_i\theta_j}$ is used for this rotation. The derivation of θ_{11} , θ_{12} , θ_{21} and θ_{22} are presented in [6].

Fig. 3. Detailed view of left (1), and right (2) cone-sphere contact points [6].

2.1 Input Cone

In Fig.4, the velocities that take place in input cone are investigated at a transmission level. The input of the system is angular velocity, and it is assigned as $\vec{\omega}_{in}^{(2)}$. $\vec{V}_L^{(2)}$ is the tangential velocity of the input cone at the $\vec{r}_2^{(2)}$ effective rotation radius that changes as the Z distance altered. Note that Z represents the position of the sphere from O_1 (see Fig.1). The calculations are presented in between (2) and (5).

Fig. 4. The illustration of the velocities taking place on the left cone (input cone).

$$\vec{\omega}_{in} = -\omega_{in} \vec{u}_3^{(2)} \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{r}_2^{(2)} = \cos \alpha_1 r_2 \vec{u}_1^{(2)} + r_2 \sin \alpha_1 \vec{u}_2^{(2)} \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{V}_L^{(2)} = \vec{\omega}_{in}^{(2)} \times \vec{r}_2^{(2)} \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{V}_L^{(2)} = r_2 \sin \alpha_1 \omega_{in} \vec{u}_1^{(2)} - \cos \alpha_1 r_2 \omega_{in} \vec{u}_2^{(2)} \quad (5)$$

2.2 Sphere

Here, the velocities taking place on the sphere is studied. First, $\vec{V}_L^{(2)}$ is resolved in the 4th frame as the tangential velocity of the sphere is aligned with $\vec{u}_2^{(4)}$ (see Fig.3.1).

$$\vec{V}_L^{(4)} = \hat{C}^{(4,2)} \vec{V}_L^{(2)} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 5. The illustration of the velocities acting on the sphere.

Next, the angular velocity of the sphere can be stated as a vector $\vec{\omega}_k^{(4)}$ which has three components including ω_1, ω_2 , and ω_3 . Note that ω_i represents the angular velocity about i^{th} axis of the relative frame. Even if $\vec{u}_1^{(4)}$ component of the $\vec{\omega}_k^{(4)}$ is not desired because it would enforce the sphere to change the Z distance, it is written to prove this situation mathematically. $\vec{R}^{(4)}$ is the radius of the sphere. Hence:

$$\vec{\omega}_k^{(4)} = \omega_1 \vec{u}_1^{(4)} + \omega_2 \vec{u}_2^{(4)} + \omega_3 \vec{u}_3^{(4)} \quad ; \quad \vec{R}^{(4)} = -R \vec{u}_1^{(4)} \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{V}_L^{(4)} = \vec{\omega}_k^{(4)} \times \vec{R}^{(4)} \rightarrow \vec{V}_L^{(4)} = [-R\omega_3] \vec{u}_2^{(4)} + [R\omega_2] \vec{u}_3^{(4)} \quad (8)$$

Equating (6) and (8) to each other and isolating ω_3 and ω_2 , (9) and (10) can be computed.

$$\omega_3 = \frac{[\omega_{in} r_2 (\cos \alpha_1 \cos \theta_{12} + \sin \alpha_1 \cos \theta_{11} \sin \theta_{12})]}{R} \quad (9)$$

$$\omega_2 = \frac{\omega_{in} r_2 \sin \alpha_1}{R} \quad (10)$$

Then, the angular velocity of the sphere is resolved in 6th frame due to the tangential velocity at the sphere-output cone contact point frame of reference. The rotations are stated as follows.

$$\mathcal{F}_4 \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_3 \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_5 \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_6$$

$$\vec{\omega}_k^{(2)} = \hat{C}^{(2,4)} \vec{\omega}_k^{(4)} \quad ; \quad \vec{\omega}_k^{(6)} = \hat{C}^{(6,2)} \vec{\omega}_k^{(2)} \quad (11)$$

Finally, $\vec{V}_R^{(6)}$ can be obtained with the help of cross product as indicated in (12). Also, $\vec{R}^{(6)}$ is the radius of the sphere (see Fig. 5.).

$$\vec{R}^{(6)} = -R \vec{u}_2^{(6)} \rightarrow \vec{V}_R^{(6)} = \vec{\omega}_k^{(6)} \times \vec{R}^{(6)} \quad (12)$$

2.3 Output Cone

In the final step, the angular velocity of the output cone is calculated by using the prior calculations. The representation of the velocities acting on this cone is illustrated in Fig.6.

Fig. 6. The illustration of the velocities acting on the output cone.

Since the rotation axis of the output cone is aligned with $\vec{u}_3^{(2)}$, the tangential velocity of the output cone ($\vec{V}_R^{(6)}$) must be transformed to 2nd frame as well. Hence:

$$\vec{V}_R^{(2)} = \hat{C}^{(2,6)} \vec{V}_R^{(6)} = \sum_{i=1}^3 V_{Ri} \vec{u}_i^{(2)}. \quad (13)$$

Then, $\vec{\omega}_{out}$ and \vec{r}_3 is written out in the 2nd frame to compute $\vec{V}_R^{(2)}$ via cross product operation. Thus:

$$\vec{\omega}_{out} = -\omega_{out} \vec{u}_3^{(2)} \quad ; \quad \vec{r}_3^{(2)} = -r_3 \cos \alpha_2 \vec{u}_1^{(2)} + r_3 \sin \alpha_2 \vec{u}_2^{(2)} \quad (14)$$

$$\vec{V}_R^{(2)} = \vec{\omega}_{out}^{(2)} \times \vec{r}_3^{(2)} \quad \rightarrow \quad \vec{V}_R^{(2)} = r_3 \sin \alpha_2 \omega_{out} \vec{u}_1^{(2)} + \cos \alpha_2 r_3 \omega_{out} \vec{u}_2^{(2)} \quad (15)$$

where $\vec{r}_3^{(2)}$ is the vector defines the contact point location with respect to the output cone's rotation axis, which is also called the effective rotation radius of the output cone. It changes as the Z distance varies. Finally, (15) and (13) are equated to each other to compute ω_{out} . Therefore:

$$\omega_{out1} = \frac{V_{R1}^{(2)}}{r_3 \sin \alpha_2} \quad ; \quad \omega_{out2} = \frac{V_{R2}^{(2)}}{r_3 \cos \alpha_2} \quad (16)$$

Furthermore, ω_{out} can be computed making use of one of the formulas presented in (16). Thus, ω_{out1} and ω_{out2} are equal to each other.

3 Verification of the Output Velocity

The output velocity of the CVT ($\vec{\omega}_{out}$) is verified through simulation studies conducted in ADAMS and Solidworks software packages. In both simulations, angular velocity is given from the input cone as an input, and $\vec{\omega}_{out}$ is obtained as a simulation result at different diameter ratios. Then, the derived formula in (16) is used making use of the same input velocity and transmission point as the simulation to compute the output velocity. In the calculations, design parameter (value) is assigned as R (17.5 mm), r_l (10 mm), L (101.12 mm), θ (0.14 rad), D (59 mm). Finally, the comparison between the simulative data and the computed data is performed to verify the calculated velocity equation (see Table 1 and Fig.7).

Fig. 7. The correlation of the simulative data graph with respect to Z distance.

The simulation parameters (values) are input angular velocity (0.349 rad/s), gravity (9806.65 mm/s²), stiffness (1149.2 N/mm), damping (0.58 N/(mm/s)), static friction (0.15), kinetic friction (0.10), solver (WSTIFF), and step size (0.001). Note that stiffness, damping, kinetic and static frictions are defined for the sphere-cone contact point, and those values are recommended as default by the used software's. Acrylic is chosen as a material for all three bodies.

Table 1. Simulation results of the velocity verification.

Z (mm)	Input Radius (mm)	Output Radius (mm)	Solidworks (rad/s)	Adams (rad/s)	Calculated (rad/s)
12	12.18	23.58	0.1798	0.1751	0.1791
15	12.63	23.13	0.1901	0.1856	0.189
20	13.38	22.38	0.2081	0.204	0.2046
38	16.08	19.68	0.2845	0.2823	0.2847
50	17.88	17.89	0.3482	0.3481	0.3490
71	21.03	14.74	0.4972	0.504	0.4996

According to the simulation results, marginal errors are observed due to the contact point definition in the simulations. To clarify, although all the theoretical calculations

are performed under the assumption of complete rigidity, it is not possible to define this type of contact in the selected simulation environments. Moreover, the error of Solidworks/Adams (Z value) in percentage is computed to be 0.39/2.23 (12 mm), 0.316/2.05 (15 mm), 1.71/0.29 (20 mm), 0.07/0.84 (38 mm), 0.229/0.257 (50 mm), 0.48/0.88 (71 mm). Finally, the mean value of overall ADAMS and Solidworks errors are reported as 1.09 %, and 0.53 %, respectively. The dissimilarities between the errors of two software's are due to the difference in the step size definition. It is defined to be 0.001 second for ADAMS whereas 0.00000001 second is set for Solidworks due to the limited power computation of the computer used for the simulations. However, these errors can be taken as acceptable within the numerical error range.

4 Conclusion

In this work, velocity-level kinematics of the recently developed CVT mechanism is studied to show its step-less speed variation characteristic. First, velocities acting on each element of the CVT are analyzed step by step, and necessary calculations are carried out to compute the velocity of the output cone in terms of design parameters. Afterward, simulations are performed in ADAMS and Solidworks software's at 8 transmission points selected unequally to validate the derived formulas. According to the results, there is a marginal error between the simulative and theoretical data mainly due to the non-rigid contact point definition in simulations. As a future study, an elastic sphere-cone contact will be formalized to reach a better formulation for the velocities. Furthermore, spin-effect analysis will be conducted by making use of this velocity-level kinematics to develop a dynamic model of this new CVT mechanism.

References

1. Mobedi, E., Dede, M.I.C.: Calibration Study of a Continuously Variable Transmission System Designed for pHRI. In: *New Trends in Mechanism and Machine Science (EuCoMeS)*, pp. 29-41. Springer, Singapore (2020).
2. Zhang, H., Solak, G., Lahr, J.G., Ajoudani, A.: SRL-VIC: A Variable Stiffness-Based Safe Reinforcement Learning for Contact-Rich Robotic Tasks. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* 9(6), 5631-5638 (2024).
3. Park, J., Lee, J., Seo H., Jeong, S.: Variable Transmission Mechanisms for Robotic Applications: A Review. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, 2–23 (2024).
4. Mobedi, E., Dede, M.I.C.: A Continuously Variable Transmission-Based Variable Stiffness Actuator for Phri: Design Optimization and Performance Verification. *ASME J. Mechanisms Robotics* 16 (8), 1-16 (2024).
5. Sclater, N.: *Mechanisms & Mechanical Devices Sourcebook*, Chapter 13. McGraw-Hill, New York (2001).
6. Mobedi, E., Dede, M.I.C.: Geometrical Analysis of a Continuously Variable Transmission System Designed for Human-Robot Interfaces. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 140, 567-585 (2019).